

ROTTLERIN. PART IV. DERIVATIVES OF ISOROTTLERIN.

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*iso*Rottlerin, described by Brockmann and Maier, is identical with the colouring matter (m. p. 181°) of Narang, Ray and Roy. Separation of rottlerin from *isorottlerin* is best effected chromatographically. Rottlerin can also be converted into *isorottlerin* by means of hydrochloric acid. *iso*Rottlerin gives a piperonylidene derivative indicating the presence of a $-\text{COCH}_2$ group.

In Part I (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1862) Narang, Ray and Roy obtained a substance, m. p. 208-9° (decomp.) by the action of nitrous acid on rottlerin methyl ether. They suggested that the substance could be represented by the formula $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_5\text{N}$ or $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}_6\text{N}$. Later on, they obtained 15.5 g. of this substance from 17 g. of rottlerin methyl ether. This indicated that the substance in question is a simple N_2O_3 -addition product and the molecule has not undergone any breakdown. Further the N_2O_3 -adduct (nitrosite) gave a dihydro derivative (dihydronitrosite) on catalytic reduction. The nitrosite and dihydronitrosite on treatment with alkali gave isomers, m. p. 152-53° and 139° respectively.

From a study of the nitrosite and its derivatives as also from the analytical data of oxide of rottlerin methyl ether, Narang, Ray and Roy came to the conclusion that rottlerin is best represented by the formula $\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_8$ with five hydroxyl groups. They have expressed this view in their various publications (*Chem. Ind.*, 1938, 57, 134; *Current Science*, 1938, 6, 333; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 393).

Narang, Ray and Roy mentioned the presence of a second yellow colouring matter, (m. p. 181°) in Kamala powder (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1863). This substance has now been more fully investigated. We have found that it can be easily separated from rottlerin if the crude rottlerin is crystallised from toluene. The toluene filtrate on concentration deposits a sticky mass which on dissolution in ether and chromatographic adsorption on alumina, separates into six zones. The first dark zone is that of rottlerin, while the second zone contains the substance, m. p. 181°. We have obtained this very substance by treating rottlerin with aqueous alcoholic hydrochloric acid. We have now come to the conclusion that this substance is identical with the substance, m. p. 180°, described by Brockmann and Maier (*Annalen*, 1938, 535, 170) subsequent to our isolation of the substance in 1937.

Brockmann and Maier (who have named this substance *isorottlerin*) have described it as a flavanone formed by isomerisation of a hydroxy-chalcone group in the molecule. At first we were also inclined to this view because *isorottlerin* methyl ether, m.p. 135-37°, gives a piperonylidene derivative and also on reduction it takes up only two atoms of hydrogen giving mainly a dihydro derivative, m.p. 209°. Therefore, it seems that one of the double bonds is involved in the formation of *isorottlerin* from *rottlerin* and a COCH₂ group is formed in the molecule which react to give the piperonylidene derivative. But the oxide of *isorottlerin* methyl ether, m.p. 120-22°, on being heated above its m.p. gives off benzaldehyde copiously. Therefore, it seems unlikely that -COCH=CHPh is involved in isomerisation. It might be mentioned here that nitrosite of *isorottlerin* methyl ether is recovered unchanged when subjected to catalytic reduction and it also gives off benzaldehyde on heating, or on treatment with alkali.

We have reduced *isorottlerin* methyl ether with zinc dust and acetic acid and isolated a substance, m.p. 162-64°. Dihydro*isorottlerin* methyl ether on similar treatment gives the same substance. This suggests that besides the double bond in *isorottlerin* methyl ether, some other group is involved in this reduction. We are engaged in elucidating this point.

For the sake of comparison we have also reduced *rottlerin* methyl ether with zinc dust and acetic acid and obtained a product, m.p. 184° (previous shrinking from 179°). It could not be acetylated with acetic anhydride and pyridine or oxidised with hydrogen peroxide and alkali. This shows that a -CHOH group has not been created in the process of reduction and the double bond in the -COCH=CHPh group has been affected. We are investigating the nature of these compounds. Oximation of *isorottlerin* methyl ether did not prove successful. The ethereal or acetic acid solution of methyl ether of *isorottlerin* on treatment with salicylaldehyde in presence of hydrogen chloride gives a permanganate-violet coloured solution but nothing crystalline separates. We are unable to say if a pyryllium salt is definitely formed.

EXPERIMENTAL.

isoRottlerin.—(a) The mother-liquor left after crystallisation of *rottlerin* from toluene was concentrated. 15 G. of the residue were treated with 150 c.c. of ether. The insoluble *isorottlerin* was collected, washed with petroleum ether and crystallised from a mixture of methyl alcohol and ethyl acetate, m.p. 180-81°.

(b) 85 G. of the residue mentioned in the above experiment were dissolved in 250 c.c. of ether. This was run through a layer of alumina set

in a long tube of 2 cm. diameter. Six zones were formed and a waxy substance was isolated from the colourless ethereal solution. The first dark zone was that of rottlerin; the second zone on elution with a mixture of ether and alcohol gave *isorottlerin*, which crystallised in pale yellow prisms, m.p. and mixed m.p. with substance isolated in (a), 180-81°. (Found: C, 69.95; H, 5.57. $C_{31}H_{30}O_8$ requires C, 70.19; H, 5.66 per cent).

Conversion of Rottlerin into isoRottlerin—A mixture of rottlerin (5 g.), alcohol (250 c.c. of 90%) and hydrochloric acid (15 c.c., d 1.15) was heated for 7 hours, the solution becoming clear after 3½ hours. The mixture on standing overnight deposited a dark red solid. The filtrate on dilution with water gave a pale yellow solid which was collected, dissolved in ether and the ethereal solution washed with sodium bicarbonate. After drying, the ethereal solution was concentrated, when the yellow solid crystallised out. This was found to be identical with the substance, m.p. 181° (mixed m.p.) obtained from natural resources. In later experiments, the yellow solid, as obtained by dilution, was purified by chromatographic absorption, yield 2g. *isoRottlerin* is very soluble in acetone, ethyl methyl ketone and chloroform. The substance as obtained in this experiment is best crystallised from a mixture of 90% alcohol and 10% benzene.

Methylation of Natural isoRottlerin.—A mixture of the natural *isorottlerin* (isolated as under *a* or *b*) (1 g.), dry potassium bicarbonate (8 g.), dimethyl sulphate (4 c.c.) and acetone (50 c.c.) was refluxed on a steam-bath for 2½ hours when the colour of the solution became pale. Dry potassium carbonate (4 g.) and 2 c.c. of dimethyl sulphate were now introduced and the heating continued for another 1½ hours when the colour of the solution became faintly yellow. Acetone was distilled off and the residue left in contact with water overnight. The semi-solid mass was collected and successively crystallised from petroleum ether and methyl alcohol, m.p. 135-38° and not 105° as wrongly reported previously (*vide*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1863). (Found: C, 71.64; H, 6.42. *isoRottlerin* tetramethyl ether, $C_{35}H_{38}O_8$ requires C, 71.67; H, 6.42% and *isorottlerin* pentamethyl ether, $C_{36}H_{40}O_8$ requires C, 72.0; H, 6.66 per cent).

Methylation of isoRottlerin Prepared from Rottlerin.—The methylation and purification of the product was carried out exactly in the same manner as in the case of the natural *isorottlerin*, m.p. 135-38°, undepressed by admixture with methyl ether obtained from the natural product. (Found: C, 71.54; H, 6.73 per cent).

A solution of piperonal (0.15 g.) and *isorottlerin* methyl ether (0.6 g.) in alcohol (8 c.c.) was boiled for 2 minutes under reflux with sodium hydroxide solution (10%, 1 mol) After the removal of most of the solvent, the

product was washed with water and crystallised in rectangular plates, m.p. 147° from ethanol. (Found : C, 71.9 ; H, 5.9. $C_{43}H_{42}O_{10}$ requires C, 71.8 ; H, 5.8% and $C_{44}H_{44}O_{10}$ requires C, 72.1 ; H, 6.0 per cent).

Oxidation of isoRottlerin methyl ether with Alkaline Hydrogen Peroxide.—The methyl ether (0.5 g.) dissolved in methyl alcohol (90 c.c.) was treated with 3 c.c. of 8% sodium hydroxide solution and 4 c.c. of hydrogen peroxide (30%). The solution was warmed to 50° for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and then left overnight. The colourless solid which separated was collected and successively crystallised from dilute and absolute methyl alcohol. It was obtained in long colourless prisms, m.p. $120-22^{\circ}$. The oxide, when heated above its m.p., gives off copious amounts of benzaldehyde. (Found : C, 69.99, 69.90 ; H, 6.43, 6.71. *iso*Rottlerin tetramethyl ether oxide, $C_{35}H_{38}O_9$, requires C, 69.77 ; H, 6.33 per cent., whereas oxide of pentamethyl ether, $C_{36}H_{40}O_9$, requires C, 70.01 ; H, 6.5 per cent).

Admixed with the oxide of rottlerin methyl ether, m.p. $127-29^{\circ}$ (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1864) it melted indefinitely at $105-110^{\circ}$.

Catalytic Reduction of isoRottlerin.—2 G. of *iso*Rottlerin, m.p. 181° (purified by repeated crystallisation) were reduced with Adam's platonic oxide catalyst in ethyl acetate solution, when 70 c.c. of hydrogen were absorbed at N.T.P. (one double bond requires 90 c.c. of hydrogen). The crude substance, obtained on removal of the solvent, was crystallised from acetic acid in colourless cubes, m.p. 209° . Reduction with palladium-charcoal also gave the same substance. If, however, only *once purified isorottlerin* (1 g.), m.p. $179-80^{\circ}$, was used, then about 130 c.c. of hydrogen were absorbed and on concentration of the solvent (ethyl acetate) a pale yellow substance (0.1 g.) separated. The mother-liquor on evaporation yielded the dihydroisorottlerin, m.p. 209° (0.7 g.). The pale yellow substance crystallised from ethyl acetate in star-shaped bunches of needles, m.p. $225-28^{\circ}$. [Found in substance (m.p. 208°) : C, 69.72 ; H, 6.02. $C_{31}H_{32}O_8$ requires C, 69.92 ; H, 6.01 per cent]. This experiment was repeated several times and in every case the product, m.p. $225-28^{\circ}$, was isolated. The product (m.p. $225-28^{\circ}$) gave [C, 68.91, H, 6.41. $(C_{11}H_{12}O_3)_n$ requires C, 68.7 ; H, 6.21 per cent. $C_{22}H_{26}O_6$ requires C, 69.1 ; H, 5.8%. $C_{22}H_{26}O_6$ requires C, 68.4 ; H, 6.7 per cent]. The *isorottlerin* used in this experiment did not appear to have more than traces of impurity as a chromatogram did not reveal any detectable second zone. Therefore, for the time being we assume that traces of impurity in the *isorottlerin* used have acted as a promoter of hydrogenolysis of the molecule and the substance is probably $C_{22}H_{24}O_6$. The C_{11} -formula seems improbable on various grounds. The substance and its mode of formation are being thoroughly examined. If it proves to be C_{22} then

our view of the C_{31} -formula for rottlerin would receive support from the consideration that $C_{22} + C_9$ (i.e. $C_6H_5CH=CH\cdot C$: extruded) makes C_{31} .

Nitrosite of isoRottlerin methyl ether.—Sodium nitrite (0.5 g.) was gradually added during 10 minutes to a solution of 0.5 g. of the methyl ether in 7.5 c.c. of acetic acid at 30° . After standing overnight the reaction mixture was diluted with water to 150 c.c., when a pale yellow substance was obtained which on crystallisation from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether and finally from absolute alcohol furnished pale yellow prisms, m.p. $194-97^\circ$ (decomp.). [Found: C, 63.36; H, 6.03. $C_{35}H_{38}O_{11}N_2$ (tetramethyl ether) requires C, 63.44; H, 5.74 per cent., while $C_{36}H_{40}O_{11}N_2$ (pentamethyl ether) requires C, 63.92; H, 5.92 per cent].

Reduction of isoRottlerin methyl ether with Zinc dust and Acetic Acid.—Zinc dust (5 g.) was added during $\frac{1}{2}$ hour to a gently boiling solution of 2 g. of the methyl ether in 40 c.c. of acetic acid. The filtrate on dilution to 250 c.c. with water furnished a white solid which crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and benzene in plates, m.p. $162-64^\circ$ (reserved for further investigation). Dihydroisorottlerin methyl ether, m.p. 209° , on similar treatment gave the same product. The substance gave a dichromate yellow colour with sulphuric acid which became dark red on warming.

For the sake of comparison, rottlerin methyl ether was reduced in a similar manner. The substance crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and ethyl acetate in irregular plates, m.p. 184° (softening from 179°). Repeated crystallisations did not improve the m.p. (Found: C, 71.9, 71.96; H, 6.78, 6.85. $C_{36}H_{42}O_8$ requires C, 71.6; H, 6.97 per cent). We will comment on this result later on. An attempt was made for catalytic reduction of the substance, m. p. 184° , with Adam's catalyst, but the original substance was recovered unchanged.

We also attempted to acetylate the substance, m.p. $178-84^\circ$, but it was unaffected. It was also not affected by alkaline hydrogen peroxide, showing that the $C_6H_5\cdot CH=CH\cdot CO$ -group is no longer present in the molecule. The non-formation of an acetyl derivative indicates that no alcoholic group is present in the molecule. Further work is in progress but the results recorded in this paper clearly demonstrate the invalidity of the rottlerin formulæ proposed by Brockmann and Maier (*loc. cit.*) and by Robertson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 309).